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Electronic Taxing And Commercial Transportation In Enugu State: Qualitative Analysis Of Drivers' Opinions

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of daily e-taxing for road transporters by the Enugu State Government ignited mixed feelings among commercial drivers. The present study examined the perceptions and attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study is estimated at 3507 commercial drivers in Enugu State. The sample size for the study is 359 commercial drivers which was determined using Taro Yamane sampling formula. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted. In-depth Interview (IDI) and Focus group Discussion (FGD) were used for data collection. Thematic approach using verbatim quotes was used for analysis. The study revealed that, commercial transportation drivers have mixed perception towards the e-ticketing, while some responded that it has reduced harassment from touts due to paying to the impersonators, other drivers lamented that paying 550 daily for ticket is exploitation by the state government, especially in this current economy conditions and hike in fuel price. Some of the commercial transportation drivers take other routes, if possible, to avoid enforcers of the e-ticketing because they are not happy with the daily e-ticketing scheme. The major challenges are network issues, low knowledge of using the electronic platform, lack of training and perceived imposition of e-ticketing scheme on the commercial drivers. The study recommended that, the state government should organise public awareness campaign for the commercial transportation drivers to sensitize them on the modalities of the e-ticketing and emblems scheme; and also subsidize the amount of the daily ticket if possible.

Keywords: e-ticketing scheme, commercial drivers, e-tax, e-emblems, perceptions, attitudes

INTRODUCTION

Tax is one of the major sources of revenue for the government at all levels. This is why government devise different means to ensure that the citizens pay their tax as at when due so that the government will have enough fund to execute projects. According to Ike and Alohan (2023) government at all levels are shifting attention to internally generated revenue to support its public expenditure. Government has embarked on various reforms and innovations focused on the need to step up collection of internally generated revenue with major attention being focused on taxation. Currently the citizen pay tax for almost everything. Maisiba and Atambo (2016) defined tax as a compulsory levy imposed by government on its citizens and business organization aimed to fulfil its core function of providing security, social amenities

and improving the general wellbeing of the society. According to Okoye and Ezejiolor (2014) the primary function of a tax system is to raise enough revenue to finance essential expenditures on the goods and services provided by government. Government generates revenue through various forms of taxes such as personal income tax, company income tax, value added tax, petroleum profit tax etc.

Over the years in Nigeria and Enugu State inclusive, tax have been collected manually by tax officers where the officers move from one position to another to collect the tax from business owners, commercial drivers, school owners and so on or request them to come to their office to pay their tax within a stipulated time, after which penalties are imposed on defaulters. Most time the tax officers employ the service of political thugs and touts to help force citizens to pay their taxes. According to Federal Inland Revenue Service [FIRS] (2015) manual tax collection and administration is bedeviled with irregularities such as impersonation of tax officers by touts, misappropriation of tax fund, fraudulent activities of tax collectors, excessive paperwork etc. which has most time led to poor tax accountability and crisis between the tax collectors and the citizens due to cases of tout harassment or fake tax officers collecting tax from the citizens. Similarly, Adegbe, Folajimi and Akinyemi (2020) stated that, manual tax in Nigeria suffered from weaknesses such as payment of taxes without evidence leading to obstruction of financial reporting, the level of compliance by Nigeria compared to other countries was abysmally low. Other problems of the manual system resulting from the earlier tax structure include iv) the absence of absolute records on each tax payers for decision making; v) absence of regular, updated and required information on taxes collected and collectable; and vi) the challenges in tax collection manually may be responsible for the gaps that existed in the estimated revenue as against its collection (Akpabi & Igbekoyi, 2019). It is in an effort to enhance tax accountability and transparency that the Nigerian government introduced electronic tax (e-tax) in 2015.

Electronic tax (e-tax) is the system where the payment, documentation, acknowledgement and administration of tax are done using electronic device over the internet or mobile application on smartphone. According to Okoye and Ezejiolor (2014) e-taxation is a system of administering tax online through electronic devices. Babatunde and Akinsanmi (2021) e-tax are the system of governmental charge collection and organization of duty procedure through an electronic medium. The electronic taxation (e-taxation) system can be described as the system of collecting taxes by the relevant authorities electronically from the taxpayers with the aid of internet service. It is an online policy which avails taxpayers the opportunity to access the service porters through the internet and see all the services offered by the tax administration like the registration for generating personal identification number, filing of returns and application for a compliance certificate (Oladele, Aribaba & Adegbe, 2020). Electronic taxation (E-taxation) and its automated processes are gradually phasing out manual tax administration globally. With e-taxation, taxpayers can conveniently pay their taxes electronically from the comfort of their homes, offices, shops and even while travelling. Tax authorities on the other hand, can now go after tax defaulters with the electronic tax history of taxpayers on their web portals (Umenweke & Ifediora, 2016).

There has been a paradigm shift in tax payment system, tax registration, tax filing, tax assessment, tax collection, and tax audit with the advent of electronic taxation (Ogunsola, 2023). In the words of David (2014), electronic taxation is a tax system that is designed and launched by revenue authority which provides electronic platform for taxpayers to access tax services with the use of computers and internet facilities. Ogunsola (2023) advised that, when introducing electronic tax system, tax authorities must ensure that the online tax platform is easy for taxpayers to use, if not, taxpayers will prefer to continue to use manual process for tax registration, filing of returns and tax payment. Electronic taxation has proved to be more efficient and effective in revenue collection, it has improved tax compliance rate, and increased tax revenue (Atika, 2012). The beauty of a new system is when the users joyfully embrace the system with the belief that the system has brought a relief for them. Electronic tax system is initiated and borne out of the desire to simplify tax process for taxpayers, and reduce the amount of efforts, time, and stress that taxpayers will normally put in during tax registration, tax filing and tax payment in a manual system.

Despite these advantages of electronic tax scheme, the introduction of daily e-tax scheme for traders and commercial transport owners by the government of Enugu State raised lots of lamentations and protest among the residence of Enugu State. According to Anukwuji (2023) Enugu State government has introduced a consolidated tax regime and e-ticketing to ensure a one-stop shop revenue collection aimed at eliminating all forms of multiple taxations and touting all revenues accruing to the state. Ajia (2024) lamented that, the multiple increases in taxes imposed by the Enugu State government has led to frustration-induced high blood pressure and the flight of businesses away from the state. According to the report, Enugu State government recently increased tenement tax for bungalows in Enugu metropolis from N30,000 to N150,000 per annum. Tenement tax for high-rise buildings in high-density areas of Enugu metropolis increased from N50,000 to N300,000. Tenement tax for high-rise buildings in low-density areas of Enugu metropolis increased from N80,000 to N400,000. Land instrument/title registration increased from N70,000 to N300,000. Also, Private school tax increased from N30,000 to N200,000 per annum. Trading shops of all kinds were forced to pay a new flat rate of N21,000 wherever they are located in the state, irrespective of the number of persons occupying them. This excludes charges for refuse disposal and management and other arbitrary charges. In timber sheds, Mr Mbah, a single poline attracts a tax of N100, in addition to the N21,000 the shop owners also pay. Daily taxes for all buses operating in the state increased from N200 to N2,000. Daily taxes for tricycles/keke increased from N100 to N450. Daily taxes for barrow pushers increased from N100 to N2,000. Small business premises tax soared to N25,000. Medium business premises tax skyrocketed to N56,000, while malls are required to pay N200,000.

Commercial drivers are expected to pay daily e-ticket of 560 naira before 12noon every weekday except Saturday and Sunday. According to Kanife (2023) Enugu State government has introduced an e-ticket for road transporters to curb the excesses of touts masquerading as government levy collectors. Head of Media to the state governor, Dan Nwomeh, the purpose of the scheme is to make tax and levy payments easier and more convenient for transporters. He also noted that the system will help eliminate multiple taxation and harassment by touts across the state. Despite these claims and potentials of e-ticketing, some of the commercial drivers in Enugu State are adjusting their operation to evade the daily e-tax, while some pay willingly. This implies that there is mixed feelings of acceptance of the daily e-tax among the commercial drivers. This study seeks to investigate the perceptions and attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards the e-ticketing and e-emblems scheme introduced by the present administration.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study is to examine the perceptions and attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards the e-ticketing and emblems scheme. Specifically, the study examine seeks to

1. Examine the perceptions of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme and emblems;
2. Ascertain the attitude of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme;
3. Examine the perceived benefits of the e-ticketing schemes to the commercial drivers in Enugu State;
4. Identify the challenges associated with the e-ticketing schemes in Enugu State;

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the perceptions of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme and e-emblems?
2. What are the attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme?
3. What are the perceived benefits of the e-ticketing schemes to the commercial drivers in Enugu State?
4. What are the challenges associated with the e-ticketing schemes in Enugu State?

RESEARCH METHODS

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. A descriptive survey is one in which a group of people or items is studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. According to Mole (2019) descriptive survey aims at collecting data on, and describing in a systematic manner, the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. Descriptive survey is therefore considered suitable for this study because it will be based on the opinions and views of commercial drivers in Enugu State on the recent daily e-ticketing and e-emblems introduced by the present government administration of the state. The population of the study is estimated at 3507 drivers, which comprised the entire commercial drivers in Enugu State which transport passengers to and from all routes in Enugu State. The sample size for the study is 359 commercial drivers which was determined using Taro Yamane sampling formula. Multi-stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the desired sample from the various motor parks in Enugu. In-depth Interview (IDI) and Focus group Discussion (FGD) were used for data collection. The researchers located the commercial drivers in the major motor parks in Enugu State and solicited their responses to the research questions and was recorded using audio recorder. The responses to be collected through In-depth Interview (IDI) and Focus group Discussion (FGD) were analyzed using Thematic approach. The audio-recorded responses were first transcribed. After the transcription, the written data were compared to find patterns of similarities and relationship. The final version was arranged into themes in line with the research questions. The thematic analysis was supported using verbatim quote from some of the commercial drivers who responded in pigeon English. Thematic Analysis is a flexible and widely used qualitative research method that focuses on identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data. It involves systematically organizing and analyzing data to identify recurring patterns, topics, or concepts that emerge from participants' experiences.

RESULTS

The collected data through in-depth interview and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) were presented according to the four research questions that guided the study. A total of 359 commercial drivers within the major cities in the state responded to the interview questions.

Research Question 1: *What are the perceptions of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme and e-emblems?*

Responses from the commercial drivers in Enugu State shows that, some of the commercial drivers believes that the current daily e-ticketing scheme and e-emblems will reduce payment of multiple taxes cause by paying to fake tax officers. Some of the commercial drivers responded that the introduction of e-ticket has reduced harassment from touts who most times are acting without the awareness of the state government. These touts force commercial drivers to pay certain amount of money that are not usually accounted for. On the contrary, some of the commercial drivers lamented that the daily e-ticket is an additional financial burden for them which adds to the recent high cost of fuel. These group of drivers wish the government will waive these daily e-ticket for them until the economy stabilize. One of the commercial drivers lamented that, "I find it difficult to save money after buying a liter of fuel for 1300 and 560 naira daily e-ticket". Another commercial driver stated that, "since the introduction of this e-ticketing we do not face harassment from touts who are fake tax officers again"

From the responses, it is obvious that there is mixed perceptions regarding the introduction of daily e-ticket by the present Enugu State administration. It was revealed that, commercial transportation drivers have mixed perception towards the e-ticketing, while some responded that it has reduced harassment from touts due to paying to the impersonators, other drivers lamented that paying 550 daily for ticket is exploitation by the state government, especially in this current economy conditions and hike in fuel price

Research Question 2: *What are the attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards e-ticketing scheme?*

Responses from the commercial drivers shows that, if they have the opportunity they will evade the daily e-ticket of 560 naira. The responses shows that some of the commercial drivers use back road to avoid the tax officers enforcing the daily e-ticket. From the responses, some of the commercial transportation drivers take other routes, if possible, to avoid enforcers of the e-ticketing because they are not happy with the daily e-ticketing scheme. One of the commercial driver stated that, "I take another route to avoid them" while another commercial driver revealed that, "if I have the opportunity I will not pay this daily e-ticket"

From the responses, the attitude of the commercial drivers towards the payment of the daily e-ticket is not positive because majority of the drivers could evade the daily e-tax if they have the opportunity to do so.

Research Question 3: *What are the perceived benefits of the e-ticketing schemes to the commercial drivers in Enugu State?*

Responses from the commercial drivers in Enugu State shows that, the major benefits of the daily e-ticketing and emblems is the elimination of paying tax, emblems or ticket money to impersonators which most often leads to misunderstanding between the authentic tax collectors and the commercial drivers. One of the drivers stated that, "since the introduction of this e-ticket there has not been case of paying tax to a fake tax officer or touts forcing drivers to pay to them" Another commercial driver stated that, "some fake officers use to collect out money and issue us fake receipt, however, the introduction of this e-ticket has stopped such cases". From the responses, it is clear that the introduction of e-ticket has some benefits for the commercial drivers and the state government as it aids accountability and transparency in tax administration and management

Research Question 4: *What are the challenges associated with the e-ticketing schemes in Enugu State?*

Responses from the commercial drivers collected through interview session shows that the challenges associated with the e-ticketing schemes in Enugu State are network issues, low knowledge of using the electronic platform, lack of training and perceived imposition of e-ticketing scheme on the commercial drivers. Additionally, one of the commercial driver stated that, there is no mechanism to allow drivers passing through Enugu State to another state to pass through without paying. Secondly, commercial driver who just arrived Enugu State after 12noon are arrested and forced to pay fine even when such driver is not within the state at the early hours of the day to pay the tax. One of the commercial drivers lamented that, "most of us do not know how to operate the e-ticket application online, and when we arrive Enugu State after 12noon we are force to pay fine for not paying out daily tax in the morning"

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The study found out that, the introduction of e-ticket has reduced harassment from touts who most times are acting without the awareness of the state government, while others feel that the daily e-tax imposed y the state government is a financial burden on them who add to their pain of buying fuel for 1300 per liter. This finding is in accordance with the report of Ajia (2024) who reported that commercial drivers and other business owners in Enugu state are lamenting the multiple increases in taxes imposed by the Enugu State government which has led to frustration-induced high blood pressure and the flight of businesses away from the state.

The findings of the study revealed that, majority of the commercial transportation drivers take other routes, if possible, to avoid enforcers of the e-ticketing because they are not happy with the daily e-ticketing scheme. The study also revealed that, the attitude of the commercial drivers towards the payment of the daily e-ticket is not positive because majority of the drivers could evade the daily e-tax if they have the opportunity to do so. The findings of the study correspond with the report of Anukwuji (2023) that commercial drivers are evading from paying the daily e-ticket once they have the opportunity. The report furthered stated that, many of the commercial drivers change routes just to evade the e-tax.

The findings of the study revealed that, the major benefits of the daily e-ticketing and emblems is the elimination of paying tax, emblems or ticket money to impersonators which most often leads to

misunderstanding between the authentic tax collectors and the commercial drivers. This is also in accordance with the report of Kanife (2023) who stated that, Enugu State government has introduced an e-ticket for road transporters to curb the excesses of touts masquerading as government levy collectors. Also, the findings further justifies the press release of the Head of Media to the state governor, Dan Nwomeh, the purpose of the scheme is to make tax and levy payments easier and more convenient for transporters. He also noted that the system will help eliminate multiple taxation and harassment by touts across the state.

The findings of the study revealed that, the major challenges associated with the e-ticketing schemes in Enugu State are network issues, low knowledge of using the electronic platform, lack of training and perceived imposition of e-ticketing scheme on the commercial drivers. There is no mechanism to allow drivers passing through Enugu State to another state to pass through without paying. Another challenge is that, commercial driver who just arrived Enugu State after 12noon are arrested and forced to pay fine even when such driver is not within the state at the early hours of the day to pay the tax.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the perceptions and attitudes of commercial drivers in Enugu State towards the e-ticketing and emblems scheme. The introduction of the daily 560 naira e-ticket by the present Enugu State administration was greeted by mixed perceptions, while some perceives it as the end to cases of paying tax to fake tax officers who are usually touts harassing commercial drivers, others perceives the e-tax scheme as additional burden for the commercial drivers in addition to the high cost of fuel in the country. It was concluded that, the commercial drivers are ready to evade the daily e-ticket if they can. The commercial drivers take another routes just to escape the tax officers enforcing the e-ticket after 12noon every day. the major benefits of the daily e-ticketing and emblems is the elimination of paying tax, emblems or ticket money to impersonators which most often leads to misunderstanding between the authentic tax collectors and the commercial drivers. The major challenges are network issues, low knowledge of using the electronic platform, lack of training and perceived imposition of e-ticketing scheme on the commercial drivers.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were suggested:

1. The state government should organise public awareness campaign for the commercial transportation drivers to sensitize them on the modalities of the e-ticketing and emblems scheme;
2. The state government should also subsidize the amount of the daily ticket if possible.
3. The government will waive these daily e-ticket for them until the economy stabilize.
4. The Southeastern government can initiate inter-regional daily tax to cover the five state instead of asking the drivers moving from one state to another within southeast to buy e-ticket in each state.

REFERENCES

- Ajia, J. (15th September 2024). LP's Edeoga urges Mbah to reevaluate Enugu tax regime. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/amp/s/punchng.com/lps-edega-urges-gov-mbah-to-reevaluate-enugu-tax-regime/%3famp>
- Akpabi, M.D. & Igbekoyi, O.S. (2019). Electronic taxation and level of awareness among some selected fast food restaurants in Lagos state, Nigeria (tax payers perspective). *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 7(7), 52-80
- Anukwuji, R. (September 21st, 2023). Enugu introduces consolidated tax regime, e-ticketing, prohibits touting. Retrieved from <https://businessday.ng/news/article/enugu-introduces-consolidated-tax-regime-e-ticketing-prohibits-touting/>
- Atika, J. (2012). Electronic Tax System Forms Part of the Revenue Collection Reforms by FIRS Whose Main Motive is Enhancing Tax Collections. *Research Journal of Business Management and Accounting*, 2(1), 1-10.

- Babatunde, D.A. & Akinsanmi, F.J.S. (2021). Impact of e-tax on revenue generation in Nigeria. *KIU Interdisciplinary Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(2), 302-312
- David, W. (2014). The Effect of Online Tax System on Tax Compliance among Small Taxpayers in East of Nairobi Tax District. Unpublished Masters of Science project, submitted to University of Nairobi, Kenya
- Ike, E. R. & Alohan, O. B. (2023). Impact of e-taxation on tax administration in Nigeria. *Proceedings of the 7th Annual International Academic Conference on Accounting and Finance Disruptive Technology: Accounting Practices, Financial and Sustainability Reporting, Rivers State University of Science and Technology University of Port Harcourt, 2023*
- Kanife, E. (8th August, 2023). Enugu state introduces e-tickets for road transporters, to launch online and USSD portals. Retrieved from <https://technext24.com/2023/08/08/enugu-e-tickets-transporters-online-ussd/>
- Maisiba, G. J., & Atambo, W. (2016). Effects of electronic- tax system on the revenue Collection Efficiency of Kenya Revenue Authority: A Case of Uasin Gishu County. *Imperial Journal of interdisciplinary research*, 3(8), 27-48.
- Muita, E.W. (2011). Factors that Influence Adoption and use of E-filing System of Kenya Revenue Authority Among Large Taxpayers: Unpublished MBA project submitted in finance department in University of Nairobi
- Ogunsola, A. (2023). Electronic taxation and tax compliance among SMES in Kogi State. *Maleté journal of accounting and finance*, 4(1), 11-24
- Okoye, P. V. C. & Ezejiolor, R. (2014). The Impact of E – Taxation on Revenue Generation in Enugu, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 2(2), 449 – 458.
- Oladele, R., Aribaba, F.O. & Adekunle, A.R. (2020). E-tax administration and tax compliance among corporate taxpayers in Nigeria, *Accounting and taxation review*, 4(3), 93-101.
- Umenweke, M. N., & Ifediora, E. S. (2016). The law and practice of electronic taxation in Nigeria: The gains and challenges. *NAUJILI*. 101-112.